

SPATIAL at the IoT Week 2022!

SPATIAL, represented by José González, CEO at AUSTRALO, one of the project's partners, took part in this amazing week by presenting the project during the "Identity, trust and privacy in an intelligent, smart IoT World. Challenges and outcomes"- Session 2: "AI and ML technologies as enablers for a more secure IoT".

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Aaron Ding (Coordinator of SPATIAL, and Director of CPI Lab at TU Delft) and Jose Gonzalez (Head of Impact in SPATIAL, and CEO of AUSTRALO) represented SPATIAL in the dedicated session for Digital Security (DS).

"Digital Services Act and Digital Markets Act set a new cornerstone for digital in Europe" What to expect about those Acts. Read more about this article created by Miguel García, project manager at Australo for SPATIAL project.

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[“We need to have explainable AI, or not use it at all”](#)

An interview with **Jon Crowcroft** from Cambridge University.

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